

WHY ARE FAIR AND OPEN DATA IMPORTANT?

FAIR stands for:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Reusable

Well-documented and openly accessible datasets enable:

- new scientific insights
- better policy decisions
- innovation in business and society
- international collaboration
- sustainable use of research funding

Open research data also enhance **transparency and reproducibility** in science.

PARTICIPATING INSTITUTIONS

- Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research
- Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH)
- GEOMAR, Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
- Technische Universität Braunschweig
- and all mareXtreme partners

CONTACT

Deutsche Allianz Meeresforschung e.V.
Markgrafenstraße 22 | 10117 Berlin | Germany
Tel. +49 0 30 23 59 627-0
kontakt@allianz-meeresforschung.de

COORDINATION

Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research
Am Handelshafen 12 | 27570 Bremerhaven | Germany
Website: <https://www.awi.de>

ENGAGE WITH DATA MANAGEMENT:

Website: <https://marextreme.de/datamanagement>
LinkedIn: mareXtreme

Data management in mareXtreme

Discovering data sets (and data treasures): Open and FAIR research data for science, policy and society

OVERVIEW

Our research investigates extreme events in the ocean and coastal regions – from tsunamis and marine heatwaves to oxygen depletion, biological risks, and storm surges. We consider both the natural processes and their impacts on society, the economy, and coastal risk management.

The research is designed to be interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary, generating valuable datasets from expeditions, observations, experiments, models, and social science approaches such as surveys.

These data are a valuable resource for future research, innovation, and evidence-based decision-making in policy and industry.

To ensure that this treasure is preserved and can be widely used, mareXtreme relies on modern research data management and open, FAIR data.

FROM EXPEDITION TO DATASET

Research in mareXtreme often begins at sea or during field campaigns on land. Researchers collect data on temperature, currents, oxygen, biodiversity, seismic activity, and many other factors, ideally in collaboration with local actors.

The data pass through the **data lifecycle**:

1. **Plan** – research questions, methods, and data management are defined
2. **Collect** – measurements, experiments, surveys, and models generate data
3. **Document** – metadata describe content, location, and methods
4. **Store** – data are structured and securely stored
5. **Analyze** – data are evaluated, interpreted, and transformed into results
6. **Publish** – datasets are made available in open data repositories
7. **Reuse** – data can be reused by researchers, policy-makers, industry, and the public

This process turns measurements into **long-term scientific resources**.

PRESERVING AND PUBLISHING DATA

Datasets from mareXtreme are published in internationally recognized data repositories, for example:

- **PANGAEA** – observational and environmental data
- **World Data Center for Climate** – Earth system model data
- **GESIS** – social science data
- **European Nucleotide Archive** – genetic data

Whenever possible, datasets are published as **open access** and assigned persistent identifiers (DOIs), ensuring they remain **discoverable and citable** over the long term.

A SHOWCASE FOR OUR DATA

The **German Marine Data Portal** is operated by partners of the German Marine Research Alliance (DAM).

Users can:

- find datasets from mareXtreme
- search metadata of more than 520,000 datasets
- visualize maps and data products

The portal makes research results visible to **science, policy, and the public**.

OUR APPROACH TO GOOD DATA MANAGEMENT

- **Standards and good scientific practice**
- **Capacity building and training**
- **Knowledge exchange and feedback processes**
- **Networking and collaboration**

The **mareXtreme data management team** is coordinated by a central data manager and consists of representatives from all four projects: **ElbeXtreme, METAscales, MULTI-MAREX, and PrimePrevention**.

It works closely with the DAM core area “Data Management and Digitalization” and contributes to the working group “Research Data Management in DAM Research Missions.”

The team supports researchers in **sustainably storing, documenting, and openly sharing their data**, and fosters **collaboration within the research mission and beyond**.

DATA FOR THE SOCIETY OF TOMORROW

Well-documented data form the foundation for new scientific insights. Researchers can analyze them using classical methods and apply artificial intelligence (AI) to identify additional patterns and relationships.

FAIR data in particular drive data-driven research, innovative applications, improved environmental and climate monitoring, and better risk prediction.

Because they are openly accessible, datasets can be used by science, policy, industry, and the public—for example, to develop new research ideas, support decision-making, and create innovative solutions and technologies.

Thus, measurements collected today become valuable treasures for future generations.

